

Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Substituted Pyrazolones used as Potential Fungicides

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Eighteen complexes have been synthesised having the composition $M(L \text{ or } L')_2X_2$ and $M'L_2Y_2$, where $M = \text{Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II)}$; $M' = \text{Co(II), Ni(II)}$; $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$; $Y = \text{ClO}_4^-$; and $L = 1\text{-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one}$ and $L' = 3\text{-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one}$. The complexes of the first category have either an octahedral or distorted-octahedral configuration and those of the second type are either tetrahedral or planar as inferred from analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral studies. These complexes have been screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* and some of the complexes are found to be active against these two pathogens.

PYRAZOLONE and its derivatives have been used widely as potential fungicides^{1,2}. Very little work has been carried out in this field of preparing metal complexes using pyrazolones as ligands³⁻⁵. In our earlier communication we have already reported⁶ the complexation behaviour and the fungitoxicity of 4, 4'-arylidene-bis-(2-pyrazolin-5-one) with Co(II) ion. The present paper describes the preparation and study of antifungal activity of some nitroso-pyrazolones co-ordinated with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Nitroso pyrazolones have been synthesised following the earlier method².

Preparation of the complexes :

An ethanolic solution of nitroso pyrazolones and metal salts were reacted separately in 1 : 2 ratio and the mixture refluxed for half an hour (in case of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one) and 1 hr (in case of 3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one) over a water bath. On keeping overnight metal complexes separated out, which were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type $M(L \text{ or } L')_2X_2$ and $M'L_2Y_2$ where $M = \text{Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)}$; $M' = \text{Co(II), Ni(II)}$; $L = 1\text{-phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one}$; $L' = 3\text{-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one}$; $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-$ and $Y = \text{ClO}_4^-$. Cobalt(II) complexes are either pink or brown except the perchlorate which

is blue in colour, the nickel(II) complexes are green, copper(II) complexes are deep green and zinc(II) complexes are white to yellowish-white in colour. All except the two perchlorate complexes have low Δ_M values (10-15 mhos cm^2) in acetone medium indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes and the conductance of the latter two are ~ 180 mhos cm^2 showing them to be 1 : 2 electrolytes. Magnetic moments of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes indicate a high spin octahedral or distorted-octahedral configuration, except the perchlorate complexes which are presumed to be tetrahedral.

The study of ir spectra is quite informative. The nitroso-pyrazolones in ethanolic medium tautomerise to corresponding oxime forms which act as bidentate ligands as there are two possible bonding sites for co-ordination with metal ions. The co-ordinated parts of these two ligands can be very well compared with diacetylmonoxime. In case of diacetylmonoxime ligand $\nu(\text{N-O})$ appears at 1015 cm^{-1} and a positive shift of $\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the chelated species is diagnostic of oxime nitrogen co-ordination⁷. But these ligands exhibit N-O stretch around 1360 cm^{-1} and decrease of this frequency by about $5-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes is indicative of co-ordination through the N-O group. The broad band $\sim 3290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in diacetylmonoxime ligand can be assigned to the stretching vibration of -OH groups⁸. In the present case two bands ~ 3320 and $\sim 1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed both in the ligands and complexes, attributable to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and $\delta(\text{OH})$ vibrations which show that oximino -OH group is free and not bonded to the metal ions. The displacement of sharp carbonyl group vibration at 1700 cm^{-1} to $\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes is suggestive of co-ordination through carbonyl oxygen atom.

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TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, IR SPECTRA AND FUNGITOXICITY DATA

Sl. No.	Compound	% Metal Found (Reqd)	% N Found (Reqd)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}=\text{O})$	ΔM mhos cm^2	μ B.M.	% inhibition at 1000 ppm conc. P.O./H.O.
1.	L	—	20.55 (20.68)	1600	1700	1360	—	—	100/95
2.	L'	—	32.95 (33.07)	1615	1705	1365	—	—	75/62
3.	$[\text{CoL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	10.74 (10.99)	15.54 (15.67)	1590	1620	1345	12.0	5.00	51/33
4.	$[\text{CoL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	9.31 (9.43)	13.38 (13.44)	1585	1625	1355	10.5	4.9	74/46
5.	$[\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	9.89 (10.006)	18.97 (19.01)	1590	1620	1350	14.8	5.1	71/34
6.	$[\text{CoL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	8.68 (8.87)	12.58 (12.65)	1595	1630	1355	18.0	4.5	47/62
7.	$[\text{CoL}_2^+(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	13.25 (13.48)	25.50 (25.63)	1585	1625	1340	12.0	5.0	89/62
8.	$[\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	10.71 (10.96)	15.47 (15.68)	1585	1625	1350	11.5	3.2	69/38
9.	$[\text{NiL}_2\text{Br}_2]$	9.29 (9.40)	13.26 (13.45)	1590	1630	1350	12.6	3.0	39/51
10.	$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	9.81 (9.97)	18.92 (19.02)	1585	1630	1355	13.3	3.1	52/54
11.	$[\text{NiL}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	8.66 (8.84)	12.58 (12.65)	1595	1625	1350	18.5	2.9	46/30
12.	$[\text{NiL}_2^+(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	13.29 (13.44)	25.53 (25.64)	1595	1620	1340	10.4	3.1	75/80
13.	$[\text{CuL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	11.53 (11.75)	15.48 (15.54)	1590	1620	1350	14.0	1.8	90/88
14.	$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	10.58 (10.70)	18.68 (18.86)	1590	1615	1335	12.5	1.75	91/64
15.	$[\text{CuL}_2^+\text{Cl}_2]$	16.14 (16.35)	21.50 (21.62)	1585	1630	1335	10.8	1.72	87/62
16.	$[\text{CuL}_2^+(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	14.16 (14.39)	25.29 (25.36)	1590	1625	1355	10.4	1.75	76/65
17.	$[\text{ZnL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$	11.83 (12.03)	15.35 (15.49)	1595	1635	1355	11.9	—	70/46
18.	$[\text{ZnL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	10.72 (10.98)	18.72 (18.81)	1590	1630	1345	14.2	—	67/35
19.	$[\text{ZnL}_2^+\text{Cl}_2]$	16.60 (16.75)	21.48 (21.52)	1595	1635	1330	12.5	—	68/43
20.	$[\text{ZnL}_2^+(\text{NO}_2)_2]$	14.69 (14.74)	25.13 (25.26)	1590	1625	1340	12.0	—	94/60

L = 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one

L' = 3-Methyl-4-nitroso-2-pyrazolin-5-one.

In case of perchlorate complexes, a broad hump appears in the $1080-1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region indicative of an ionic perchlorate group which is in conformity with some earlier observations^{9,10}. The conductance data are also in support of ionic nature of the perchlorate showing 1 : 2 electrolytic nature.

In the electronic spectra of cobalt(II) chloride, bromide and nitrate complexes, two absorption bands are observed around 20.6 (18) and 8.5 (15) kK regions assignable¹¹ to octahedral environment. The perchlorate complex exhibits two intense bands at 16.00 (1450) and 8.9 (200) kK regions suggesting a tetrahedral geometry. Nickel(II) chloride, bromide and nitrate complexes show three bands $\sim 9-5$ (6.5), 15.0 (7) and 25.0 (15) kK regions assignable to the characteristic of octahedral environment. For the perchlorate complex, bands observed at 16.0 (190) and 8.2 (30) provide evidence for tetrahedral geometry of the complex. Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band ~ 14.5 (35) kK region indicating probably a distorted-octahedral configuration. Zinc(II) complexes are presumably octahedral on the basis of analysis, conductance and ir spectral data.

All these complexes prepared during the present investigation have been assayed for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* using spore germination tests at various concentrations by the standard method¹². The nitroso pyrazolones used as ligands possess significant fungicidal activity. It was observed that the complexes Sl. No. 4, 5, 7, 8, 12-20 exhibited encouraging activity while the remaining complexes were found inactive against the pathogen *P. oryzae*. Highest activity was exhibited by the complex Sl. No. 20, which inhibited 67, 94% of *P. oryzae* spore germination at 250 ppm and 1000 ppm concentrations respectively. The complexes (Sl.

No. 6, 7, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 20) exhibited significant activity against *H. oryzae* spore germination, while the remaining complexes were found inactive.

The fungicidal activities of the prepared complexes were compared with the standard fungicides like O-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphoro dithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, Difolatan 50% WP, Derosal 60% WP which inhibited 95, 98, 87% of spore germination of the pathogen *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration respectively. It was noted that five complexes (Sl. No. 7, 13, 14, 15, 20) showed activity comparable with the standard fungicides and hence can be tried for commercial fungicides.

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